

New Challenges in the Implementation and Exploitation of a Low-Cost Web Map of the Active Deformation Areas across Europe

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Abstract: The European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) is already offering data on Persistent Scatterers (PS) throughout Europe, which will aid in analyzing ground deformation on a continental scale. However, to more fully comprehend ground motion processes, it is preferable to use Active Deformation Areas (ADA) instead of PS. The CTTC has been using its ADAfinder tool to generate ADAs since 2018. With the new availability of EGMS PS data for the entire continent, the CTTC is now working on producing ADAs for all of Europe and making them accessible to the public through a self-developed, in-house hosted, web-based map application. A former paper describes the initial steps taken to develop it. This work focuses on how the challenge of processing a huge amount of data has affected the design and implementation of the tools used in the data production workflow. Additionally, the manner in which the EGMS data is structured, providing data sets that spatially overlap, has resulted in a new problem: overlapping ADAs. The approach to resolving this issue is also discussed in this paper. The result is an evolution of the initial concept where not only economic reasons but also considerations on automation and handling of large volumes of data have guided the design and implementation of the system.

1 INTRODUCTION

The European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) [European Environment Agency, 2021] has already provided billions of Point Scatterers (PS) data for the whole of Europe [Crosetto et al., 2020], which will be a valuable tool for analyzing ground deformation processes at a continental level. However, Active Deformation Areas (ADA) are a more effective means of understanding these processes as they depict areas where actual deformation is occurring, which reduces the amount of information to analyze. Figure 1 illustrates an area covered by several ADAs, with colors indicating up to four levels of certainty of the findings.

[Barra et al., 2017] describe the methodology for identifying ADAs, which involve creating a polygon that encircles the affected area, and computing the aforesaid level of certainty. This helps experts to focus their efforts on areas that actually require their expertise. The CTTC developed in 2018 a tool,

Figure 1: ADAs and their reliability. The white bullets inside the ADAs are the PS used to build them.

ADAfinder, that implements this methodology and has been in use since. [Tomás et al., 2019, Navarro et al., 2020] provide more detailed description of ADAfinder and other related tools.

As part of the SARAI project, funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MCIN), the CTTC is working on publishing ADAs online for the entire European continent by creating a web map application specifically for this purpose. This section briefly reviews the technologies used to devise and implement not only the web map application but also

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the several software components targeted at producing the data to be published—that is, to transform the PS delivered by the EGMS into ADAs stored in a database accessed by the said web application, namely the data production pipeline and workflow. This review is provided for the sake of completeness, since the interested reader may find a much more detailed description in [Navarro et al., 2022]. Note, however, that the web application has evolved since the publication of the aforementioned paper, so any relevant changes will be discussed where appropriate.

Why not the cloud? The initial problem to be solved was determining where the information about ADAs and the web map application would be stored. The initial plan of using the cloud was rejected due to the high cost it incurred (thousands of euros per year). Therefore, an in-house solution was chosen. An existing server was repurposed to host both the data and the applications.

Server hardware. The repurposed server had 32 GB of RAM, an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4790 CPU @ 3.60GHz / 8 cores processor, and a 7 Tb RAID 1 SATA disk system.

Server software. Keeping the cost low. The required software modules to set up the web map application were chosen from the open-source and free market. These included:

- PostgreSQL [The PostgreSQL Global Development Group, 2021] plus PostGIS [PostGIS Project Steering Committee, 2021] for storing geospatial data - the ADAs.
- GeoServer - a web-based tool for publishing geospatial data, which retrieves information from a database such as PostgreSQL and makes it available via standard web-based protocols. See [OSGEO, 2021].
- Apache [The Apache Software Foundation, 2021b] + Tomcat [The Apache Software Foundation, 2021a] are httpd and Java servers respectively - to run both GeoServer and the web map application.
- Finally, the web map is a self-developed tool programmed in JavaScript and HTML. It relies directly on GeoServer to retrieve the ADA data it displays.

Producing the ADAs. The ADA are generated through a software pipeline that includes:

- ADAfinder - a self-developed tool that has been in use since 2018, which takes the PS delivered by the EGMS as input to produce the ADAs.
- ADA2PGIS - a tool specifically created for this project, it takes the ADAs created by ADAfinder

Figure 2: The original data production workflow. Source: [Navarro et al., 2022]

and produces a series of SQL-compliant files, which include the same information but in a format that can be used to interact with the database.

- psql - a command-line tool that is included with PostgreSQL, used to execute the files provided by ADA2PGIS and insert the ADAs into the database.

This workflow, oriented at processing a single EGMS data set at a time, is depicted by Figure 2. Note that once a data set has been processed as described it is inserted into the database, which makes it immediately accessible via the web application.

The web map application. It has been developed using JavaScript and HTML and it is aimed at the visualization of the stored ADAs. It may zoom, pan, and filter data by combining up to three criteria such as the mean velocity of the ADAs or their quality assessment value. Different background layers, such as OpenStreetMaps, Google Satellite, or Google Terrain can be chosen. When an ADA is clicked on, information about its attributes, including its averaged deformation time series, is displayed. Figure 3 shows the web application, depicting an ADA, its attribute table and time deformation series. The legend, filters and other controls as well as the attribute data table are located at the right side of the image, while the map itself is shown on the left. The original version of the application showed the time deformation series as a numeric table; the current one, as seen in the said figure, already presents an interactive chart. Additionally, the current version may tell apart ADAs originating from either ascending or descending orbits.

Figure 3: The web map application.

From this point, and once the EGMS data were available, it became clear that the next goal to accomplish was to build a system capable of dealing with the processing and management of very large volumes of data.

The rest of this document is organized as follows: section 2 discusses the new challenges that had to be faced and the solutions adopted to address them once that the initial system moved from a preparatory to a production stage; more specifically, it highlights the need to automate the production workflow to manage huge volumes of data as well as the problem of overlapping data sets producing repeated ADAs. Finally, to conclude, section 3 analyzes how the original system needed to evolve from a design standpoint where economical reasons prevailed to a real-life situation where the volume of data to handle became the actual driver of the process.

2 THE NEW CHALLENGES

Since this project started long before the EGMS made the PS data generally available, it was possible to design and implement both the web application and the data pipeline tools taking into account not only the purely algorithmic aspects but also those related to the volume of information to handle; although there was no indication about how big the final number of PS would be, it was quite clear that it would be big

enough as to take it into account as a design and implementation principle for the software to develop.

ADAFinder, the application identifying the ADAs already existed and had been designed taking the problem of data volume in mind. In fact, it is usual to process input files with as many as five million PS without problems. The same idea was kept in mind when implementing ADA2PGIS and, of course, the web application itself. In this last case, two aspects were considered: (1) the storage required to keep the high volume of ADAs obtained and (2) the performance of the server that should host the web application. As stated in section 1, a RAID system was installed in the server which was big enough to hold millions of ADA data; to check the performance of the system, hundreds of thousands of synthetic ADAs were inserted into the PostGIS database and the web application was able to display them without problems.

The preceding paragraphs aim to show that considerations for handling a significant amount of data were taken into account from the very beginning. Nonetheless, and once that data from the EGMS became available, it was evident that not all the facets of the problem had been foreseen. These were mainly two: (1) the need to take into account the automation of some processes due to the aforesaid overabundance of data and (2) the problems created by the way in which said data is organized, creating areas where information overlaps thus leading to repeated outputs. The following subsections elaborate on these

new challenges and how they have been addressed.

2.1 Simplifying the Operational Aspects

The workflow depicted in Figure 2 explains how the PS delivered by the EGMS are converted into data stored in the server database. This workflow is fully operational and produces correct results. However, it was conceived to process *a single data set at once*.

A data set, in this context, is the minimum item that may be downloaded from the EGMS web site. It defines, consequently, the granularity of the operations; in other words, since the workflow in Figure 2 is conceived to process one of these data sets, to finish the project, every single available data set must be processed.

Considering that there are about 15,000 data sets and all of them need to be processed to complete the project, it should be clear that a lot of human intervention is required. Such a situation implies that the total time needed to process all the data will be significantly increased compared to a more automated procedure. Furthermore, the greater the human intervention involved in the process, the greater the probability of errors. Therefore, it seemed clear to the development team that the already implemented workflow needed to be improved to simplify the operational aspects of the process.

Automation, however, is conditioned by a tough prerequisite: uniformity. The ADAfinder step, that is, identifying ADAs using the PS as input, is a task that requires adjusting a series of parameters that usually depend on the input data (as, for instance, the size of the pixel used in the input imagery, see [Barra et al., 2017]). On the other hand, the ADAs published on the web, should be obtained using a set of identical parameters, since, otherwise, the results for different geographical areas could not be compared. This makes it possible to go for a solution where the level of automation is much higher. The handicap is to find a reasonable set of suitable set of parameters to run ADAfinder for all Europe. This is a task currently undergoing.

At any rate, and since automation is not only desirable but possible, a new set of tools have already been implemented to make it possible. These are:

- A script that makes possible to run ADAfinder for *all* the data sets (EGMS data) stored in a single directory. The same set of parameters will be used for every data set. All results are stored in the same output folder.
- A new application, *automateADA2PGIS*, will run ADA2PGIS—the step that transforms the output

of ADAfinder into something suitable to be inserted in the server's database—for all the input files (ADAfinder-compatible ones) found in the same directory. Again, all its outputs will be stored in a unique folder.

Each time that ADA2PGIS is run, a set of output files is created; some of them contain SQL (Standard Query Language) commands and the last one is a batch (shell) file that will take care of actually performing the process of inserting the ADAs included in these SQL files into the database. Since *automateADA2PGIS* will run ADA2PGIS for all the inputs found in some directory, there will be an equivalent number of outputs. This means that if the number of input data sets is n , also n batch (shell) files will be created, each of them taking care of inserting their respective ADAs. This number n is, in fact, the total number of items that may be downloaded from the EGMS, which amounts to *about 15,000*. Consequently, the operator should run, by hand, all these shell files to complete the process, which is, again, a lengthy and tedious procedure, prone to human errors. To avoid this situation, *automateADA2PGIS* also create a so-called "master batch file" that takes care of running each of the individual batch files for every data set. This completes the automation of the process.

To summarize, the automation of the data production pipeline could be (but it is not, see section 2.3) the following one:

1. Download the whole EGMS data sets. Store these in the same directory, namely the EGMS folder.
2. Run the ADAfinder automated script, taking as input all the files stored in the EGMS folder. All outputs are stored in the same output directory, namely the ADAfinder folder. This step identifies the ADAs.
3. Run the *automateADA2PGIS* tool, taking as input the files stored in the ADAfinder folder. All outputs are stored in the same output directory, namely the *automateADA2PGIS* folder. This step transforms the whole set of ADAs into a format that may be used to insert them into a database (files with SQL commands). A master batch file is generated, controlling the execution of the individual batch files output by each run of ADA2PGIS—which is executed by *automateADA2PGIS*.
4. Run the master batch file. This step will insert the whole set of ADAs into the server's database.

Note that the workflow above first downloads *all* the data sets from the EGMS (step 1) to process them

Figure 4: Overlapping EGMS data sets (northeast of Spain).

later at once (steps 2 to 4) thanks to the high level of automation achieved with the script to run ADAfinder and the automateADA2PGIS tool. Of course, it would be possible to proceed downloading smaller groups of EGMS data sets, fully process them, and start again until the project is finished. The reason to adopt this approach (process everything at once at every step) is due to some restrictions set by a new problem: the overlapping of ADAs. Section 2.2 describes this issue, how it has been solved and how it affects the overall production workflow.

2.2 Removing Overlapping ADAs

The EGMS has divided the surface of Europe into tiles; each of these tiles is the minimum unit of download and, therefore, of processing within the workflow. As already mentioned, about 15,000 tiles have been necessary to cover the entire territory for which PS data is available.

These tiles overlap with their neighbors. This phenomenon can be observed in Figure 4. This is a problem from the point of view of data processing, since *duplicate* information is generated.

The ADAfinder application is the one affected by this information overlapping problem. This tool is used to identify the ADAs of a certain area of the terrain (the tile) using the PS existing in that area. When run with some tile as input, it will produce ADAs located in areas shared with other tiles. When ADAfinder processes any of these other tiles that are adjacent to the first one, it is very likely that it will find new ADAs in the common, overlapped zones.

Some of these new ADAs are not really new, but the same ones that had been detected previously. Their shape or extent may vary slightly as the number of PS included in the overlapping zones of adjacent tiles may change, but ultimately they are still the same ADAs.

Figure 5 depicts this problem. More specifically,

Figure 5(a) shows ADAs in an overlapping area that were created from PS in two different tiles, namely *a* and *b*. Purple ADAs were identified when processing tile *a* and the orange ones come from tile *b*. Here it can be seen how the ADAs of tile *a* overlap with those that come from the processing of tile *b*. Their shapes, as already mentioned, are not identical due to the total number of points available in each data set, but it is clear that the ADAs in question represent the same area and that it does not make sense to store them all in the server's database.

This was the reason to develop a new tool, *purge_overlaps*: removing overlapping ADAs.

This tool had to solve two different problems:

1. Decide, and implement, *which are the ADAs to remove* when overlapping exists and
2. actually remove overlaps *for all Europe at once*.

Concerning the **first problem** above, the decision taken was to remove the smaller ADAs. That is, when two or more ADAs overlap, only the one whose area is the largest of all is preserved. With this approximation, it is intended to keep the ADA that most reliably represents how the terrain has been deformed. Obviously, some information may be lost, as smaller ADAs whose surface include zones *not* covered by the one being retained may be removed. In the example shown in Figure 5(a) two smaller purple ADAs overlap with the bigger orange one, which is the one that is preserved (see Figure 5(b)). The same is true for the single smallest purple ADA that overlaps with another orange one at the top of the figure: it is removed in favor of the one with the largest area.

The criterion used to decide if two ADAs overlap is the intersection ratio, that is, the area of the intersecting zone divided by the area of the ADA itself. This is a parameter whose value may (and must) be set by the user. For example, if it is set to x , a couple of ADAs for which *all* their overlapping areas have an intersection percentage lower than x will be considered as non overlapping, while if this x is exceeded by any of them the decision is just the opposite: they overlap.

The **second problem**, having to remove all the overlapping ADAs for all Europe at once is due, also, to the overlapping of the tiles (see again Figure 4). The reason is that although it would be possible to check the overlaps stepwise, that is, checking these for only a couple of tiles at a time, this would significantly complicate the management of the process. A tile t overlaps with a number of other tiles, and this is recursive situation: that is, all the tiles that overlapped with t also overlaps with other tiles that are not t , and so on. This means that the number of tile overlaps

Figure 5: Removing overlapping ADAs.

to manage is very high. Consequently, purging overlaps by tile couples would become a long and tedious process, highly prone to human error due to the large number of pairs to process and the management overhead required to ensure no duplicate work is done.

This is, therefore, a clear candidate for task automation. The new tool `purge_overlaps` has been developed to solve this problem. It takes the whole set of outputs of `ADAfinder` for all Europe as inputs to perform the purge of overlapping ADAs. The initial

estimate of the total number of ADAs to be processed places this number below 1,000,000, which is a very reasonable amount of data to manage by a computer program, so this should not pose an implementation problem. On the contrary, the process of finding what are the couples of ADAs that *do* intersect, computing their areas and the intersection between overlapping candidates might imply a costly computational burden if an inappropriate algorithm would be used. Fortunately, computer science offers techniques to successfully address this problem, techniques that have been adopted by `purge_overlaps`, so that its performance is satisfactory.

2.3 The New Workflow

Although `purge_overlaps` solves the problem of the overlapping ADAs, the use of this program imposes a restriction on the overall production workflow: it is not possible to fully process just a subset of tiles (i.e. going from the download to the insertion of the ADAs in the server database) and repeat these steps with some other subsets until all the data from the EGMS has been processed. This is so due to the need to purge overlapping ADAs at once, that is, only when the ADAs for all Europe are finally available.

Taking into account this restriction, the new, final workflow is as described below:

1. Download the PS from the EGMS.
2. Identify the ADAs using the automated script to run `ADAfinder`

The two previous steps may be executed repeatedly, combining them to download some data and then identifying the ADAs for a certain number of data sets. That is, it is not strictly necessary to wait until all Europe has been downloaded to proceed to identify their ADAs at once. At any rate, and no matter how these two steps are combined, all ADAs must have been processed before proceeding to step 3 due to the requirements set by `purge_overlaps` (see section 2.2), that is, all ADAs must exist before this tool is run. Consequently, the conversion of ADAs to SQL format is performed too in a single automated step (number 4):

3. Purge the overlapping ADAs for all the data sets covering Europe at once.
4. Convert all remaining ADAs (those not purged at the previous step) to SQL format using `automateADA2PGIS`. This tool takes care of running the original `ADA2PGIS` tool for all the data sets involved in the process.
5. Run the master batch file created by `automateADA2PGIS`, which takes care of performing

Figure 6: The new workflow.

the actual insertion of all data into the database. This step makes the information immediately available to the web application.

Figure 6 depicts graphically the workflow above.

3 CONCLUSIONS

In [Navarro et al., 2022] the authors presented a first attempt to implement a server capable of publishing the Active Deformation Areas for the whole of Europe; in that work, the main aspect taken into account were the economical restrictions that prevented using the regular solutions available for this kind of problems, such as hosting both data and software in the cloud. It is worth noting that the issues related to the data processing pipeline and the volume of information to be handled were already considered; the new software developed for the project (i.e., ADA2PGIS)

was designed and implemented keeping in mind the need to automate a production workflow and how much information needed to be managed; additionally, the web server was configured to be able to store and display millions of ADAs. The performance of both the server and the software were tested with synthetic data to ensure that processing and publishing the ADAs from across Europe was possible using a low-cost solution. In short, this was the goal of that work: to show the feasibility of such a system.

It may be said, therefore, that the authors considered, from the very beginning, not only the technical aspects of a project of this type but also those issues related to real-life aspects that only show up when the actual exploitation of the system begins. The authors, therefore, felt quite comfortable thinking that everything was ready to start the identification and publishing of ADAs.

Data from the EGMS was finally available by the beginning of November, 2022. This event was the trigger to switch from a test environment to a production one. As soon as the actual magnitude of the task (the number of data sets to download and process, their spatial distribution with overlapping tiles) was finally known, the problems described in section 2 were made evident; the development of the scripts to automate ADAfinder or the automateADA2PGIS tool immediately began, and the new workflow, taking into account such changes, was designed.

At the moment of writing this paper, the personnel responsible for the exploitation of the system is still downloading the complete data sets of PS from the EGMS servers—in other words, it has been decided to execute steps 1 and 2 in the workflow described in section 2.3 at once: first, everything is downloaded, then ADAs from across Europe are identified to then proceed to the remaining steps in the workflow. Therefore, and since the exploitation of the system is still at a very early stage, no other issues have arisen yet; the authors consider this possibility as remote, but it cannot, however, be discarded. Thus, and concerning future work, the foreseen activities are (1) those strictly related to the pure production tasks as described in section 2.3 and Figure 6 so all the ADAs of all Europe are made available to the general public; then, (2) to cope with any problems that the software applications might experience due to the high volumes of data to process, since, as stated above, said problems may not be yet discarded and (3), assuming the success of this project and building on the experience gained, take a few more steps further to create a new web application to show, again at the continental level and using the same EGMS data, wide-area differential deformation maps indicat-

ing the gradient of the deformation field—in this case, the basic software to produce such results is still under development.

To finish, it is worth to state that this paper is targeted at two goals; the first one, describing the low-cost system that the CTTC has developed to provide public ADA data at a continental level; the second, but no less important aim, is highlighting something that is generally forgotten or at least overlooked when systems similar to the one described in [Navarro et al., 2022] and in this very same work are designed, developed and put into operation: that not only the algorithms, software or hardware are important, but also that the operational aspects related with their routine exploitation or the characteristics of the data to handle *do* play a very important role in how these are created and later on, exploited. Even worse, not considering aspects such as automation or the reduction of human intervention may very well increase the risk of failure for these projects.

The authors foresee that the web map will be made available to the general public during the first half of 2023.

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